

**BULGARIAN CULINARY VERBS:
GRAMMATICAL ASPECT AND SITUATION TYPES**

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Abstract: The article gives an overview of the way new verbs are added to the Bulgarian Culinary Lexicon, a part of the Multilingual Culinary Lexicon, with special attention to their categorisation into the situation types proposed by Zeno Vendler: states, activities, accomplishments, achievements. Based on the lexico-grammatical category of the verb aspect in Bulgarian, a classification scheme for categorising verbs into different situation types has been developed. A brief comparison is made between languages such as English and Italian, in which the verb aspect is not a lexico-grammatical category, and Bulgarian. It is shown that the Bulgarian verbs of the secondary imperfective aspect and the verbs in English and Italian behave similarly with regard to their aspectual interpretation in context and thus exhibit a similar categorisation into situation types.

Keywords: *Multilingual Culinary Lexicon, Bulgarian Culinary Lexicon, situation types, verb aspect*

1. Introduction

A few years ago, the Multilingual Culinary Lexicon (CulNet)¹ was published, an online language resource containing data on food, cooking and culinary topics in twenty-five languages (Koeva 2022). During our work on the ontology of activity predicates, a relatively large number of verbs belonging to the culinary domain were selected. This paper is devoted to the description of the way they are included into the Multilingual Culinary Lexicon, which can be considered as a synchronous effort together with the development of the **Dialect Culinary Dictionary** for Bulgarian.

At the centre of our work is the development of a classification scheme according to which the Bulgarian imperfective and perfective verbs can be assigned to situation types (in many cases with the help of their derivation): States, activities, accomplishments, achievements. Some of the classifications are unambiguous, while

¹ <https://dcl.bas.bg/culnet-2020/>

others require more information from the wider context (lexical context, temporal categories², status of nominal actants) for disambiguation. The distinction between ambiguous and unambiguous cases can serve as a starting point for comparative studies and some computational approaches to natural language processing.

The article is organised as follows: Section 2. briefly introduces the Multilingual Culinary Lexicon; Section 3. explains the main principles of organising lexical and semantic information when adding new verbs to the lexicon. Section 4. contains a brief presentation of the situation types and a classification scheme for the distribution of Bulgarian verbs among the situation types based on the verb aspect and the different types of verb derivation. Some correspondences with languages such as English and Italian are briefly explained.

2. Multilingual Culinary Lexicon in brief

The Multilingual Culinary Lexicon is primarily based on the WordNet structure (namely the Princeton WordNet³ and the Bulgarian WordNet⁴) – a (lexical) semantic network whose nodes represent synonyms (synonym sets, synsets) denoting concepts linked with connecting arcs encoding different types of relations – semantic: genus-kind, part-whole, etc.; morphosemantic: predicate-agent, predicate-instrument, etc.; derivational; extra-linguistic; interlingual: translation equivalents into English (Miller 1986; Fellbaum 1998).

For example, the verbs {меля; смилам; смеля} ‘за храна – надробявам на много малки парченца’ form a synset and are related to their equivalent concept in English, which is represented by the synset {mince} ‘cut into small pieces’⁵. This synset is linked to a more general concept – the **hypernym**: in Bulgarian {нацепя; нацепвам; накълцвам; накълцам; кълцам} ‘режа нещо на парчета с брадва или друг груб остър инструмент’ and in English {chop; chop up} ‘cut into pieces’, which is outside the culinary terminology. The words that have a derivational relations in Bulgarian and English are: {мелачка} ‘кухненско пособие за рязане или кълцане на дребно на хранителни продукти (месо, зеленчуци и т.н.)’ and {mincer; mincing machine} ‘a kitchen utensil that cuts or chops food (especially meat) into small pieces’; and only in English: {mince} ‘food chopped into small bits’. These derivational relations show that the morphosyntactic relation **has instrument** exists between the synsets {меля; смилам; смеля} and {мелачка} in Bulgarian and

² The term *temporal categories* is used to summarise the related categories of tense, grammatical aspect and mood.

³ <https://wordnet.princeton.edu>

⁴ <https://dcl.bas.bg/bulnet/>

⁵ Synonyms, definitions and other related information are taken either from the Bulgarian Culinary Lexicon, which is based on Bulgarian WordNet, or from Princeton WordNet and have been adapted by the author where necessary.

{mince} and {mincer; mincing machine} in English; and that the morphosyntactic relation **has result** exists between the verb synset {mince} and the noun synset {mince} in English.

Bulgarian in the Multilingual Culinary Lexicon is linked to 23 languages for which wordnets are available on the basis of equivalence relations to English: Albanian, Basque, Catalan, Croatian, Danish, Dutch, French, Finnish, Galician, Greek, Hebrew, Italian, Icelandic, Lithuanian, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian, Russian, Serbian, Slovak, Slovene, Spanish and Swedish. Not all concepts are available for all languages. The following information is accessible online: Synonyms, definition, immediate hypernym, category, ingredients for Bulgarian and English; synonyms for all languages and definitions – if available for a language. For example, the concept {меля; смилам; смеля} is related to equivalent synsets from other languages (if they are already included in the respective wordnets): {esbocinar; esmicar; esmicolar} in Catalan; {kosati; sjeckati} in Croatian; {hienontaa} in Finnish; {sminuzzare; tritare} in Italian; {desmenuzar; picar} in Spanish, etc.

Before our efforts, the Bulgarian Culinary Lexicon comprises 3,222 synsets, of which 2,936 synsets are nouns, 224 synsets are verbs and 62 synsets are adjectives. In total, there are 5,338 synonyms (some contains only one word).

3. Adding new verbs to the Multilingual Culinary Lexicon

When reviewing some culinary books in Bulgarian and English, we realised that some of the verbs used in this field are not yet included in the Multilingual Culinary Lexicon. In general, three cases can be observed: i) the English verb has no lexicalization in Bulgarian; ii) The verb is not present in the Princeton Wordnet but does not exist in English, i.e. it is language-specific to Bulgarian; iii) the verb is present in the Princeton Wordnet but is not yet included in the Multilingual Culinary Lexicon. These cases presuppose the corresponding activities:

i) Including an “empty” node corresponding to the English synset for which the concept has not been lexicalised in Bulgarian; the verb is presented descriptively and the definition is marked with the expression “no lexicalisation”. For example, the English concept {baste} with a definition ‘cover with liquid before cooking’ is not lexicalised in Bulgarian and it is translated as {поливам със сос, вино, вода} with the definition ‘no lexicalisation – подготвям храна преди готвене, като я заливам с течността, в която ще се пече: сос, мазнина, вино, вода и под.’.

ii) Adding the selected synsets to the Bulgarian WordNet, labelling them as language-specific and adding lexicographical data for Bulgarian: explanatory definitions, examples, grammatical and stylistic labels. One such example is the verbs {преточа, преточвам} with the meaning ‘източвам течността от туршия (обикновено при приготвяне на кисело зеле) и я вливам отново в същия съд, където е била, за да се улесни ферментацията’.

iii) Inclusion of the selected synsets in the Bulgarian WordNet as translation equivalents to the corresponding English synsets from the Princeton WordNet and

addition of lexicographical data for Bulgarian: explanatory definitions, examples, grammatical and stylistic labels. For example, the synset {обезкостявам; обезкостя} ‘отстранявам костите от месо’ equal to {bone; debone} ‘remove the bones from’ has not yet been included in the Multilingual Culinary Lexicon, although it is available in the Bulgarian WordNet.

A more complicated example is the synset {точа, разточвам, разточа} ‘с точене в различни посоки приготвям кори от тесто’ which is not yet included in the Multilingual Culinary Lexicon. There is a synset {точа, разточвам, разточа} with the more general meaning ‘правя нещо да бъде плоско и равно на дебелина чрез натискане с ваялк, ролка или по такъв начин’ corresponding to the English synset {roll out; roll} ‘flatten or spread with a roller’. The decision in favour of the more specific meaning should either be included as a language-specific concept or omitted.

Following the structure of the Bulgarian Culinary Lexicon, the new verb entries contain synonyms, grammatical and stylistic labels, explanatory definitions and examples. The synsets are linked by conceptual and extra-linguistic relations; however, only hypernymy-troponymy relationships are displayed in the online version of CulNet.

In this phase of work, 52 new verb synsets were added to the Multilingual Culinary Lexicon that have an equivalence relation to English (both those that were already present in the Bulgarian wordnet and those for which there is no lexicalisation in English), and 39 synsets were identified in English for which there is no lexicalisation in Bulgarian. The most important principles of lexical-semantic description, which follow earlier conventions (Koeva 2022), are briefly explained below.

3.1. Synsets

In some cases there is only one word for the synset, but the synonymous sets usually contain synonyms. The synonyms (called literals) can be simple words, compound words or multi-word expressions. It is very rare for Bulgarian verb synsets to contain only one verb, as the verbs of the imperfective and perfective aspect are artificially combined as synonyms. For example, the synset {зачервявам, зачервя} ‘пържа (или пека) хранителни продукти или ястие, докато придобият червеникавокафяв цвят’ and its English counterpart {brown} ‘fry in a pan until it changes colour’: the Bulgarian imperfective verb and the perfective verb are present in the same synset. Multi-word expressions (words that denote a single concept but consist of two or more orthographic words) can be identified by a series of tests: whether they have as a synonym a simple word {пека на грил; гриловам} {grill} ‘cook over a grill’; whether they have as a translation equivalent a simple word in another language {спазвам диета} {diet} ‘follow a regimen or a diet, e.g. for health reasons’, etc. (Koeva 2022: 26).

3.2. Definitions

According to the conventions for the construction of the Bulgarian WordNet, the definitions for Bulgarian synsets are subject to the following principles: i) presentation of the meaning in the way it has been adopted for the definitions in monolingual general dictionaries; ii) originality of the definition: no repetition of the definitions in existing dictionaries (this is mainly achieved by adding more information to the definitions); iii) use of a specific structure not only for different word classes but also for the specific lexical sets (Atkins and Rundell 2008: 124) within a single word class.

The definition of verbs is subject to the same conventions and, if possible, contains information about the arguments. The definitions of verbs representing one and the same semantic frame – encyclopaedic knowledge structures or conceptualisations underlying the meaning of sets of lexical items (Fillmore 2003: 288) – are linked by explicating one and the same (mental) model (Atkins 1996: 540–541). Although the number of verbs in CulNet is relatively small, such an approach provides semantic coherence in the description of verbs that evoke a particular semantic frame (which is not the case with conventional dictionaries).

For example, the verb synset {закусвам; закуся} has the definition ‘приемам първото за деня хранене (обикновено рано сутринта)’ (breakfast: to have the first meal of the day, usually early in the morning) and the verb {вечерям} – the definitions ‘приемам последното за деня хранене, обикновено надвечер или вечер’ (dine: to have the last meal of the day, usually in the evening or early at night). In the Princeton WordNet, the definitions are as follows: ‘eat an early morning meal’ and ‘have supper; eat dinner’.

3.3. Examples

At least one example is added to illustrate the meaning of the synsets. The examples are (usually) in the form of complete sentences and were created in different ways: by searching and selecting in corpora or by own construction.

3.4. Lexical and Conceptual Relations

The Multilingual Culinary Lexicon contains (following WordNet) two types of relations: between literals and between synsets (called conceptual). The conceptual relations apply to all synonyms in the two connected synsets, while the lexical relations connect words within one or two synonymous sets.

The conceptual relations between verb synsets are: **hypernymy**, **troponymy**, **subevent**, **is a subevent of**, **causes**, **is caused by**, **verb group**, **also see**. The lexical relations are semantic: synonymy and antonymy and derivational. The derivational relations taken from the Princeton WordNet are at the level of synsets, and the most common general relation is called **derivative in English**. Some of the derivational

relations were checked, and if the relation proved to be valid for Bulgarian, the relation **derivative in Bulgarian** was introduced. If there is a derivational relation between two words, then there is also a semantic relation of a certain type between the respective synsets that contain them (a so-called morphosemantic relation) (Fellbaum et al. 2007). Morphosemantic relations are, for example: **has agent / is agent of** between {ловя риба} {to fish} and {рибар} {fisherman}.

3.5. Stylistic and Grammatical Labels

If there is a particular usage – an inferior word, a figurative meaning, a phraseological meaning, an obsolete word, an informal usage, etc. – a label is added to the respective synonym. The labelling system developed for Bulgarian (Коева 2021b: 55–56) reflects stylistic and grammatical differences in the use of synonyms.

The grammatical labels indicate a constant grammatical property of a particular word. To distinguish between verbs with different aspects, each verb is labelled as follows: perfective verb: {замеся} ‘knead’, imperfective verb: {замесвам} ‘knead’, a verb that can function as a perfective or imperfective verb depending on the context: {бланширам} ‘blanch’, an imperfective verb without a perfective equivalent: {месея} ‘am kneading’, a perfective verb without an imperfective equivalent: {гостя} ‘regale’ (just one example from the Culinary Lexicon).

4. Verb aspect and situation types

The information about verbs in the Bulgarian Culinary Lexicon, which is part of the Bulgarian WordNet, namely the categorisation of the verb aspect as well as the information about whether they are formed with a prefix, suffix or both, can be used to determine on a lexical level whether verbs belong to one of the four classes defined by Zeno Vendler (1957):

States are characterised as static (or non-dynamic), durative and atelic (without a definite endpoint). They are homogeneous, i.e. the situation described remains the same in each temporal segment of its duration, and they have no inherent endpoint. Examples are: *помня* ‘remember’, *мразя* ‘hate’, *живея в* ‘live’.

In contrast, **activities** are dynamic, durative and also atelic. Like states, they are homogeneous – each temporal segment involves the same continuous action, but they inherently involve movement or change. Examples are: *плувам* ‘swim’, *режа* ‘cut’, *пия* ‘drink’.

Accomplishments, on the other hand, are dynamic, durative and telic. They are not homogeneous, they have a preliminary stage as an activity that ends with a change of state. Examples are: *да изпържа пиле* ‘roast a chicken’, *да сваря зеленчуци* ‘cook vegetables’, *да изям ябълка* ‘eat an apple’.

Finally, **achievements** are dynamic, non-durative (momentary) and telic. They are not homogeneous and occur instantaneously and represent a punctual transition. Examples are: *да мигна* ‘blink’, *да глътна* ‘swallow’, *да сръбна* ‘sip’.

About 100 Bulgarian verbs from the Multilingual Culinary Lexicon are categorised into situation types. We are not aware of any distribution of verbs for a particular language in the classes of Z. Vendler, and it seems tempting to use the semantics of the verb aspect in Bulgarian to distribute the Bulgarian verbs into the appropriate situation types. The reason for this is the opinion that the semantic content of the lexico-grammatical category verb aspect in Bulgarian is based on the relation between the action and its endpoint, regardless of the speaker, the person of the verb and the utterance. It is generally assumed that the most important semantic opposition in the category is the private opposition “completeness: incompleteness” with the main meaning of the unmarked member “processivity” (Kutsarov 2007: 551). The feature of completeness is to be considered as follows: Verbs in the perfect aspect represent the action in its complete execution, regardless of its temporal location, its actual duration or its single or multiple execution (Ivanova 1983: 257).

Several studies have shown the correlation between the Slavic verb aspect and the distribution of verbs in the situation types. In brief it has been argued (Charalozova 2009) that Bulgarian verbs denoting states and indefinite processes (activities) are imperfective and have no perfective counterparts. Verbs that denote finite processes (accomplishments) are imperfective (they express a process that is moving towards its limit) and perfective (they denote an event, a result of this process): *хвърлям* ‘am throwing’ and *хвърля* ‘throw’; *пиша* ‘am writing’ and *напиша* ‘write’. And verbs that denote an event (achievements) can also be perfective and imperfective, with the imperfective denoting the same event, but repeated several times and conceived as a process: *намеря* ‘find up’, *намирам* ‘am finding up’; *напиша* ‘write up’, *написвам* ‘write up’. Similar is the view of S. Rangelov (2017) who also classified as accomplishments verbs like: *виждам* ‘am seeing’, *видя* ‘see’, *избухвам* ‘am exploding’, *избухна* ‘explode’. More generally, it has been also stated that atelic verbs (which lack the indication of a boundary) are only imperfective: *зная* ‘know’, *лежа* ‘lie’, *гранича* ‘border’, *тичам* ‘run’, *пея* ‘sing’ (Nitsolova 2008: 248).

For Russian, it is shown that states and indefinite processes are expressed by imperfective verbs (Paducheva 1996: 92). Verbs imperfectiva tantum can express permanent properties and relations (*contain*, *contradict*), temporary states (*look*, *smell*) and permanent states (*love*, *know*) (Paducheva 1996: 126).

Our categorisation of verbs into situation types focuses on the lexical meaning and word formation of perfective and imperfective verbs. For some groups of verbs, the categorisation remains ambiguous, since their assignment to a certain semantic type can only be clarified by contextual use. The proposed categorisation shows for which verbs the combination of grammatical aspect and lexical meaning allows a prediction of the situation type and for which the context is necessary.

In Bulgarian, **states** are some primary imperfective verbs (verbs without a prefix or suffix): *горчи* ‘is bitter’, *зная* ‘know’⁶, some imperfective verbs formed

⁶ Examples from other areas are given for some classes that are not yet represented in the Culinary lexicon.

with prefixes from primary imperfective verbs: *принадлежа* ‘belong’; with the suffix *-н-* from Old Bulgarian roots: *мръзна* ‘am cold’; or with imperfective suffixes from nouns or adjectives: *студувам* ‘am cold’, *младея* ‘look young’ (Коева 2021a: 141–142). The imperfective verbs are categorised into states and activities according to their core meaning (stative or dynamic). It is not surprising that there are hardly any state verbs in culinary lexis.

Activities are some primary imperfective verbs (verbs without a prefix or suffix): *пия* ‘drink’, *ям* ‘eat’, with the suffix *-н-* from Old Bulgarian roots: *кисна* ‘soak’, *плагна* ‘rinse’; and with the imperfective suffixes *-ув-* (*-стевув-*), *-ов-*, *-в-*, from nouns or adjectives: *обядвам* ‘have lunch’, *вечерям* ‘dine’.

Perfective verbs are: i) a small number of non-derivative (primary) verbs (*дам* ‘give’); ii) verbs that are formed from imperfective or perfective verbs by adding prefixes (*изпека* ‘bake up’ from *пека* ‘bake’, *препържва* ‘fry up’ from *пържва* ‘fry’) and iii) verbs that are formed from imperfective verbs by adding the suffix *-н-* (*бодна* ‘prick up’ from *бода* ‘prick’, *кипна* ‘seethe up’ from *кипя* ‘seethe’). Depending on whether the verbs describe a durative or momentary situation, the first two groups are categorised as **accomplishments** or **achievements** according to their lexical meaning. The verbs formed with the suffix *-н-* are only **achievements**. The semantic difference between accomplishments and achievements is sometimes small, which is why some scholars do not categorise them into two types.

Imperfective verbs (secondary imperfective verbs) derived from perfective verbs with suffixes: *-а-* (*-’а-*), *-ва-*, *-ава-*, (*-’ава-*), *-ува-*, can be categorised into different situation types depending on the steps of derivation:

i) The imperfective verbs that are formed with suffixes from primary perfective verbs (without a prefix or suffix): *давам* ‘give’ from *дам* ‘give’, *купувам* ‘buy’ from *купя* ‘buy’, *раждам* ‘give birth’ from *родя* ‘give birth’, can be **activities** or (**accomplishments** / **achievements**) depending on the lexical meaning of the verb. Activities can also function as accomplishments or achievements depending on the context in which they are used (understood in the broadest sense as grammatical and/ or lexical context).

ii) Imperfective verbs (secondary imperfectives), which are derived with suffixes from prefixed perfective verbs, can occur as **activities** or (**accomplishments** / **achievements**) depending on the lexical meaning of the verb. Activities can also function as accomplishments or achievements depending on the context in which they are used.

1. *Приготвям* бульона в продължение на един час. (activity)

‘I have been preparing the broth for an hour.’

2. *Ще приготвя* бульона за пет минути. (accomplishment)

‘I will prepare the broth in five minutes.’

It has already been pointed out that the secondary imperfective aspect has two components in its semantics: an achieved goal and continuity. When the goal is

contextually actualised, the secondary imperfectives explicate one of the options, and when the continuity is actualised, the other (Ivanchev 1976: 134 – 143).

iii) Suffixed prefixed imperfective verbs, part of the tetrad: primary perfective – suffixed imperfective – prefixed perfective – suffixed prefixed imperfective, are **activities**, since they can be considered as directly derived from the suffixed imperfective verb and have therefore inherited its properties. For example, *платя* ‘pay’, *платяам* ‘am paying’, *изплатя* ‘pay off’, *изплатяам* ‘am paying off’. As already mentioned, only one primary perfective verb was identified in the culinary domain, which does not form such a tetrad.

3. *Цял ден изплатяам заплати.* (activity)

‘I pay salaries all day long.’

4. *Акушерката изразжда детето в продължение на часове.* (activity)

‘The midwife delivers the child for hours.’

Again, activities can function as accomplishments or achievements depending on the context in which they are used.

iv) Imperfective verbs, parts of the tetrad: primary imperfective – suffixed perfective – prefixed perfective – suffixed prefixed imperfective, can be **accomplishments** or **achievements** depending on their lexical meaning. They are derived directly from the prefixed perfective verb.

5. *Режа морковите в продължение на 30 минути.* (activity)

‘I am cutting carrots for 30 minutes.’

6. *Ще резна от моркова едно парченце.* (achievement)

‘I will cut a piece of carrot.’

7. *Ще нарежа морковите за 5 минути.* (accomplishment)

‘I will cut carrots in 5 minutes.’

8. *Нарязвам морковите за 5 минути.* (accomplishment)

‘I cut carrots in 5 minutes.’

Finally, there are the so-called biaspectual verbs, which are interpreted in context as perfective or imperfective verbs. We can consider them as imperfective (by-form) verbs, which are interpreted as **activities** or **accomplishments** depending on the context, or as verbs that are neutral on the lexical level for the category of verb aspect.

9. *Карамелизирам пуканки цял час.* (activity)

‘I caramelize the popcorn for an hour.’

10. *Ще карамелизирам пуканките за 5 минути.* (accomplishment)

‘I will caramelize the popcorn for 5 minutes.’

We consider these verbs to be aspect-less and it has been shown that the aspect in such cases can only be assigned compositionally (Kabakchiev 2020: 118 – 121).

In languages such as English and Italian, where the verb aspect is not a lexicogrammatical category, the interpretation of the development of the situation or the

verb that expresses it can be done in two ways – by temporal categories or by context. Bulgarian verbs with secondary imperfective aspect and verbs in English and Italian therefore behave similarly.

In linguistics, the term grammatical aspect refers to the use of certain verb forms to express how a speaker represents the internal temporal structure of a situation. Semantically, aspects offer different perspectives on the development of a situation (Declerck et al. 2006: 28). In English, only progressive and non-progressive aspects are consistently marked with verb forms. Some scholars also distinguish a perfect aspect, which reflects the relevance or outcome of a situation at a later point in time (Declerck et al. 2006: 29). In Italian, if you want to express something more immediate or an action that is still in progress and not yet completed at the present moment, you can use the progressive form of the present tense. The progressive present tense is similar to the English ‘to be doing something’ (Proudfoot and Cardo, 2005: 151). When it comes to events in the past that are considered completed, Italian uses the perfect aspect: the simple perfect or *passato remoto* and the compound perfect or *passato prossimo*. The *passato prossimo* is very similar to the English present perfect (‘I have eaten’, etc.); however, they do not always coincide exactly in their use (Proudfoot and Cardo, 155–156)

For verbs in English and Italian (and in some other languages) as well as for the biaspectual verbs in Bulgarian, the grammatical aspect, i.e. the progressive and the perfect aspect, can be used to disambiguate the aspectual class (lexical aspect) depending on the context. The grammatical aspect is also relevant for the shift from activity to accomplishment. In all cases, the grammatical aspect acts cumulatively with the context of the verb phrase or clause, and the final aspectual interpretation is formed gradually (Verkuyl 1972; 1993).

5. Conclusion

The Multilingual Culinary Lexicon is a subset of WordNet. Recently, more culinary verbs have been added to the resource, and their classification with grammatical labels for the verb aspect raises the question of the categorisation of Bulgarian verbs into the four situation types: states, activities, accomplishments and achievements. Based on the lexico-grammatical category of verb aspect in Bulgarian, a classification scheme for categorising verbs into different situation types was developed and presented here. The categorisation of Bulgarian verbs into situation types depends - with the exception of the so-called biaspectual verbs – primarily on their lexical meaning and the lexico-grammatical aspect (which can be considered as part of the meaning of a verb), taking into account the stages of derivation between different verbs. In addition, shifts between activities and accomplishments (achievements) can be observed due to the different temporal (grammatical) categories and the different context of the verb phrase / clause in which the verb is used. Bulgarian biaspectual verbs behave similarly to verbs in some languages for

which there is no lexico-grammatical aspect: only the temporal categories and the context are relevant for their interpretation. Other lexical aspect shifts can also be observed (e.g. activities to states (*Той куца към училище, защото се удари* ‘He limps to school because he has injured himself’; *Той куца от дете* ‘He has limped since childhood’), but these are not mentioned here.

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БЪЛГАРСКИ ГЛАГОЛИ, СВЪРЗАНИ С КУЛИНАРИЯ: ВИД НА ГЛАГОЛА И СИТУАЦИОННИ ТИПОВЕ

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Резюме: Статията прави общ преглед на начина, по който се включват нови глаголи в *Българския кулинарен уърднет*, част от *Многоезиковия кулинарен лексикон*, с акцент върху категоризирането им в ситуационните типове, предложени от З. Вендлер: състояния, действия, постижения, изпълнения. Разработена е класификационна схема за категоризиране на глаголите в различни ситуационни типове въз основа на глаголния вид в български език. Прави се кратко сравнение между езици като английски и италиански, в които глаголният аспект не е лексикално-граматична категория, и български. Показва се, че българските глаголи от т. нар. вторичен несвършен вид и глаголите в английски и италиански език се държат сходно по отношение на аспектвалната си интерпретация в контекст и имат сходна категоризация в ситуационни типове.

Ключови думи: *Многоезиков кулинарен лексикон, Български кулинарен лексикон, ситуационни типове, вид на глагола*

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